

netWorked Youth Research for **Empowerment** in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

WYRED Research Cycle Overview Infographic

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1 Introduction

WYRED (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) is a H2020 project that aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, but also a platform from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes.

This infographic presents an overview of a WYRED research cycle. One cycle is composed by four stages:

1. Preparation: In this first stage stakeholders, children and young people express their views on the most important issues that concern young people in the digital society.
2. Dialogue: In the second stage, children and young people engage with each other in dialogues to define the exact questions that they would like to focus on.
3. Research: In the third stage children and young people design and carry out social research projects to explore these questions, and find answers, together or individually.
4. Evaluation: In the final stage, children and young people devise appropriate ways to explain their results and recommendations to government and society.

The detailed activities of these stages are explained in this infographic (WYRED Consortium, 2017).

2 Infographic

The image file of this infographic is available at <https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/840> or directly at https://repositorio.grial.eu/bitstream/grial/840/1/WYRED_WP1_D1.1_Participants-01png.png.

3 Citation

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